

An inexpensive kerosene light trap to monitor rice insects

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An inexpensive kerosene light trap tested in Philippine rice fields in 1978 is highly attractive to the following insects: *Scirpophaga incertulas*, *S. innotata*, *Chilo suppressalis*, *Sesamia inferens*, *Nymphula depunctalis*, *Cnaphalocrosis medinalis*, *Nilaparvata lugens*, *Nephotettix virescens*, *N. nigropictus*, *Sogatella furcifera*, *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis*, *Naranga aenescens*, and *Rivula atimeta*.

The lantern is an improvement of that presented in the *1970 Rice production manual*. The light source is a fisherman's kerosene lantern designed for outdoor use. Village tinsmiths can easily make it with locally available materials. Each lantern costs about US \$4. It uses only a few cents worth of kerosene per night and produces a bright white light. The funnel-shaped exhaust cap extends 4 cm down into the lantern body and efficiently removes the small amount of soot that accumulates on the inside of the glass (see figure). Rain does not affect the lantern's performance. The lantern, attached to a wooden or bamboo support frame, hangs above the rice crop.

The frame has a platform that supports a basin of water (see photo). Cooking oil that is added covers the water surface and immobilizes fallen insects. Experience shows that baffles are not necessary. The insects hit the lantern and fall into the water basin below. Farmers, who have been taught to recognize each important species, can collect and count insects daily. We are now correlating daily catches with field populations. We hope that farmers and extension technicians can use the trap as a tool in forecasting.

1. Design of the lantern with handle. IRRI Entomology Department.

The kerosene lantern can be made inexpensively from local materials. IRRI Entomology Department.

Litsinger, J.A. and Entomology Department. 1979. An inexpensive kerosene light trap to monitor rice insects. *Int. Rice Res. Newsl.* 4(2):17. N17